

GHAFUR GHULAM- HIS CREATION IS AN EXCELLENT BONFIRE, HIS EVERY APPEARANCE IS A VARIETY OF BURNING: POET OF UZBEK, TAJIK AND OTHER FRATERNALS

Bakhromova Laylo Rayim kizi

Tashkent state university of law, second year student
of Faculty of Public law
laylorayimovna@gmail.com
+998941891807

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7542989>

Anotation: This article covers the life and work of one of the brightest manifestations of Uzbek literature, Gafur Ghulam, and now contains historical events dedicated to the memory of the writer. Also there are the opinions of Uzbek, Tajik, Russian and other related folk writers about the writer.

Keywords: story, short story, poem, House-Museum, Rasul Hamzatov, Nikolai Tikhonov, Genghis Aitmatov, Abdullah Kahhor, Konstantin Simonov.

One of the famous writers of Uzbek literature, Gafur Ghulam, was born on May 10, 1903 in the Kurgontegi neighborhood of the city of Tashkent. At the age of nine, he became an orphan from his father, at the age of fifteen from his mother, Gafur received his first education in the old school, and then in the Russian school. He graduated from the teacher training course after *the coup of October* and worked as a teacher in the schools.

Since 1923, he worked as a director and educator in the orphanage and, then worked in the editorial office of the newspapers which are named "Qizil O'zbekiston", "Kambag'al dehqon" va "SHarq haqiqati". The newspaper plays the role of "dorilfun" for him, became an important tool on the way to studying the life of the people, to actively intervene in it. His first collections of poems entitled "Dinamo" (Dynamo) and "Tirik qo'shiqlar" (Living songs), collected from his triumphal poems about the defense of the country, his comedies condemning of the past and works applauding the Daily creative work of the people, were published in 1931-1932. In 1930-1935, the poet created the epic "Ko'kan" (Kokhan), ballads "To'y" (Wedding), "Ikki vasiqa" (Two acts).

However, it was felt that a number of poems by the poet, in particular, the epic "Ko'kan", which we have praised for many years as a major work on the topic of collectivization, are not at the level of requirements of the current era. In particular, there is no realistic expression on the fact that the commended collective policy totally caused endless tragedies among certain positive results. In his poems about the party, Motherland, Lenin, October, the trends of

modernity are also noticeable. Thanks to this, the poet's work today requires a critical approach.

True, the writer revised some of his works created under the influence of the cult of personality as early as the time of death. He wrote some verses a new, giving the poem naturalness and vitality. The same is characteristic of his poems "Kuzatish" (Observation), "Sen yetim emassan" (You are not an orphanage), which were also reworked by the writer.

In the 1930s, Ghafur Ghulam also created such short stories as the story, the line of felethons "Netay" (the name of a girl), "Yodgor" The name of a boy), "the resurrected corpse".

During the war years, the poet focused the entire temperature of his creativity on the people fighting the fascist invaders, creating poems imbued with the spirit of confidence in his inevitable victory. He wrote poems, publicistic essays and articles such as "Sen yetim emassan" (you are not an orphan), "Kuzatish" (observation), "Vaqt" (time) , " Sog'inish" (longing), and shot the people to the victory of battle and labor. Ghafur Ghulam, in many types of literary genres even in the post-war years, created highly artistic works, published a number of excellent articles on publicistics and literary criticism. His work was manifested as a kind of Chronicle of the life of the people during this period.

If Ghafur Ghulam rose to the level of a philosopher poet with his poetic works during this period, the story "Shum bola" (A naughty boy), with stories such as " Mening o'g'rigina bolam" (my thief child), demonstrated that he was a skilled prose writer who knew the people's life and spirit well. Gafur Ghulam also made a great contribution to the arrival of the Uzbek translation school on the field. He, like Othello, King Lear, translated skilfully into of world and Russian literature into Uzbek. Gafur Ghulam was a full member of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan (1943). He was awarded the honorary title of people's poet of Uzbekistan on the occasion of his 60th anniversary (1963). Many of the poet's works have been translated into the languages of the peoples of Asia and Europe. Gafur Ghulam, a fiery Herald of Uzbek poetry, a huge word artist, died in Tashkent on July 10, 1966. Posthumously awarded the order of the great merit (2000).

So far, in memory of the writer, kata events have been organized throughout our republic. A scientific and theoretical conference dedicated to the 115th anniversary of the birth of Gafur Gulom was organized at the Writers ' Union of Uzbekistan in cooperation with the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Culture, the Gafur Gulom House-Museum. Those who spoke in it

noted that the creative works are of particular importance in their content, rich in Hajj and philosophy, reflecting the mentality, traditions and traditions of the Uzbek people, dreams.

At this point, to remember the writer's House-Museum. The Gafur Ghulam House-Museum consists of a 2-storey house, where the poet lived and worked in 1944-1966. It included a literary exposition and memorial complex. Special stands show translations of the creator and examples of his work in the academic field. The third Hall of the museum is occupied by exhibits that show the love, respect of the people for the proud. In honor of Ghafur Ghulam, the metro station, a large literary publishing house, the Museum of local lore in Kokand are also named of him. There are also documents on the celebration of the 90th and 95th anniversary of the poet.

At this point, let's dwell on the thoughts of the great about the ghouls of the ghouls.

Konstantin Simonov: "In my imagination, it is difficult for a poet to distinguish a cave from a human cave. He was the perfect person. That is why it is impossible to separate his poems from his life and, on the contrary, from his life poems. Both in life and in poems, he was a person with a soul, he sincerely loved people."

Abdullah Kahhor: "Ghafur Ghulam- his creation is an excellent Bonfire, his every appearance is a variety of burning, that is, light and temperature is the excellent strength, charm, dazzling beauty of the Ghulam train."

Nikolai Tikhonov: "I am a Russian poet. When they asked what news Ghulam brought to World Poetry, I would say that the Uzbek poet praised the joys of life, portrayed a new Asian person, sang an Oriental Song he created. The new person he described changed the image of his dear land... he glorified Uzbek poetry, the work of the Uzbek people with his poetic talent."

Genghis Aitmatov: "Ghafur Ghulam is a wonderful word artist who made a great contribution to the development of poetry of Turkic peoples, one of the most beautiful representatives of our entire multinational literature, the pride of all of us."

Mirzo Tursunzadeh: " Ghafur Ghulam is my soulful friend and mentor: the more Uzbek he is, the greater the poet of both the Tajik people and our other brothers."

Rasul Hamzatov: "The immortal, living poems of Gafur Ghulam resonate today in their native language - Uzbek, Russian and other fraternal peoples and foreign

languages. Ghafur Ghulam is a people's poet. No matter what language it is translated into, it will live long and forever.”

List of used literature:

1. <https://tafakkur.net/gafur-gulom.haqida>
2. Newspaper of "Xalq so'zi" 2018.16.04
3. Selected works. Ghafur Ghulam. 2012
4. Website "O'zbekiston arboblari".

WOC
WORLD
ONLINE
CONFERENCES

